

PASS information

Title	An Observational Post-Authorisation Safety Study to Assess the Safety of COVID-19 vaccine
Protocol number	VAC31xxx
Protocol version	3.0
Protocol date	09 December 2022
Statistical Analysis Plan version	1.1
Statistical Analysis Plan date	16/05/2023
Version identifier of the feasibility assessment report 2	V1
Date	12/09/2023
EU Post Authorisation Study (PAS) register number	
Active substance	COVID-19 vaccine
Medicinal product	
Product reference	
Procedure number	EMEA/H/C
Marketing Authorisation Holder (MAH)	
Joint PASS	No